

ARTIFICIAL INTELLIGENCE AND MACHINE LEARNING APPLICATION IN FOOD PROCESSING AND ITS POTENTIAL IN INDUSTRY 4.0

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ABSTRACT

Food is essential for human survival. Some of the most crucial factors to think about are minimising food waste, optimising the supply chain, and enhancing food logistics, delivery, and safety. The achievement of these goals is greatly aided by the application of AI and ML. Proliferation of ever-more-powerful and pervasive computer networks has enabled modern logistical and industrial systems. Within these networks, there is a continual influx of fresh data from many sources, generated by sensors, equipment, systems, intelligent devices, and humans. Thanks to computers' ever-improving capabilities, we can now analyse Big Data more quickly, thoroughly, and in-depth than ever before. These developments have rejuvenated and ushered in a new era called Industry 4.0 or the Smart Factory, which has increased the importance of artificial intelligence technology (AI). Machine learning and artificial intelligence are discussed in this article within the context of the food industry and business. Important uses of this technique include supply chain optimisation, crop selection, logistics, food distribution, and processing plant predicting maintenance.

Keywords: AI In Food Industry, Machine Learning; Smart Farming; Internet of Things; Sustainable Management; Food Quality; Food Safety.

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INTRODUCTION

In general, we do not take into consideration the role that technology plays in the food industry while we are talking about the food industry. However, in today's food industry, especially in the production and delivery procedures, technology is dominating.

Applications on our smartphones allow us to locate meals, and we can also obtain information about the manufacturers of those items. This is made possible using technology. Product shelf life can also be improved with the use of technology in the food sector, which also helps in the creation of different types of packaging and contributes to the preservation of product quality and safety. Technology has resulted in a reduction in the expenses of production while simultaneously resulting in a considerable improvement in the quality of food [1]. The use of AI in the food and drink production process is a hallmark of Industry 4.0, which is often called the fourth industrial revolution. Artificial intelligence has already begun to have an impact on several sectors within the food and beverage manufacturing industry. In many ways, machine learning is changing the way companies handle food safety standards, product development, predictive maintenance, and supply chain management.

A process that brings together many industries is the manufacturing of food. The company must keep its technology up to date, find new ways to improve its operations, and maintain a greater emphasis on technological innovation to maintain its position in the competitive marketplace. Machines programmed with artificial intelligence may learn from complex calculations and data analysis, allowing them to make educated decisions [2]. This contributes to the automation and optimisation of processes in the food business, which reduces costs and human error significantly. Machine learning and artificial intelligence are also used in the food industry. The food production business is not the only one that has showed its support for AI and ML; restaurants, pubs, and cafés like Starbucks have done the same.

The application of artificial intelligence technologies inside the industry framework has the potential to create more secure and exact product manufacturing lines, as well as superior speed and consistency, compared to human labour [3].

Figure 1. Effects of AI and ML on the Agrofood and Fast-Moving Consumer Goods industries.

The use of AI in supply networks is widespread around the globe. Artificial intelligence (AI) is integrated into every step of the process, from production to the supply chain, where it is used for tasks such as product level monitoring and labelling. In this paper, we will go over a lot of ground: what is AI, how it has developed over the years, how it is currently being used in the food industry, how it affects food safety, what are the pros and cons of using AI in food processing, what effects AI has had on food processing, and what the future holds for AI in food processing [4].

The food industry has always had one foot in the agricultural sector, even before it started. The supply of raw materials accessible to the Fast-Moving Consumer Goods (FMCG) sectors can be enhanced if agricultural output is enhanced. To produce and manufacture their goods, many companies rely on these basic ingredients [5]. Many people's lives have been profoundly affected by the COVID-19 pandemic, which has wreaked havoc on these businesses' supply chains. The government's decision to declare a state of emergency led to the global suspension of numerous businesses, affecting every link in the supply chain from farmers to consumers [7-9].

The unexpected decline in production and revenue, the fall in oil prices, the loss of tourist receipts, the challenges linked to climate change, and perhaps other causes could all be attributed to the Covid-19 pandemic. There has been an increase in the number of people who are hungry and malnourished in recent years, according to the Food and Agriculture Organisation of the United Nations (FAO) [8]. However, by utilising high-tech automated systems and incorporating artificial intelligence and machine learning into crop management, the agriculture industry can improve crop production and increase the quantity and quality of raw materials available to the food industry. Figure 1 illustrates the influence that artificial intelligence has had on the food and fast-moving consumer goods industry. In this section, we will cover a few of the machine learning technologies that have been implemented in the agricultural sector and have helped to improve crop management.

LITERATURE REVIEW

The Early Situation in the Food Industry

Efficiency in food production and processing was a primary goal in the early days of the food industry's development [9], which led to an emphasis on creating better hardware, equipment, and processing procedures. To keep up with the ever-increasing demand for food while maintaining its high quality, these technical advancements were crucial. Improving agricultural equipment and methods was a key effort to boost crop productivity and quality in the early days of the food business.

To improve processing efficiency and keep food fresh, stone mills and presses were progressively adopted as agricultural production progressed. Concurrently, advancements in food processing led to the development of procedures like curing, drying, and smoking, which allowed for the preservation and transportation of foods with longer shelf lives. Not only did the early food business prioritise the development of processing and hardware technologies, but they also placed a premium on efficiently connecting the entire food chain. Excessive inventory and food waste resulted from inefficient supply chain management caused by a lack of close cooperation and information exchange among merchants, processors, and manufacturers of raw materials. A more extensive supply chain management system has been initiated by the food industry to address this issue [10]. Logistics and inventory management have been made more efficient with the use of IT-enabled improvements to data exchange and sharing across various segments.

At the same time, the food sector has taken steps like standardisation and quality certification to boost trust and collaboration among the various parts in the chain, making it easier to track where food comes from and how good it is. Finally, the food business has, from its start, responded to the ever-increasing demand for food by developing more efficient processing methods, hardware, and equipment to boost processing and production efficiency.

In the food industry, for example, a more comprehensive system for managing the supply chain has enabled all links in the chain to function together efficiently, from the production of raw materials to the consumption of completed items, paving the way for future success and expansion.

The Current State of the Food Industry

Agricultural, fishing, and cattle operations are all part of the food sector, which now encompasses many different fields, including as food processing, retail, and food service [11]. From farming to fork to plate, it encompasses the whole food value chain and is a massive international business. There is a growing demand for safe, secure food, and customers have a wide variety of options to choose from. Some of these new technologies, such as blockchain, 3D printing, artificial intelligence, and big data, find extensive use in the food business. Utilising this cutting-edge technology has the potential to boost efficiency, cut down on waste, enhance food safety and quality, boost demand, and hold on to customers.

The Importance of Food Safety

The security of our food supply has been a major issue for quite some time. Establishing a safety traceability system is critical for ensuring food safety and generating revenue for food supply chain components [12]. Standing at the intersection of food safety, big data, information technology, and the internet, the food safety cloud seeks to enhance the capacity of government agencies to anticipate information that is sensitive to food safety and to swiftly identify recurring and emerging significant concerns related to food safety through the analysis of big data. People can eat more healthily and safely with the support of personalised nutrition programming, standards, information on the origin and composition of food, and other dietary structuring advice and personalised services. There has been tremendous progress in the field of food safety thanks to machine-learning technologies in identifying potential sources of food contamination [13].

It is possible to train the model to examine several process variables—including chemical composition, humidity, and temperature—by using a supervised learning approach. This programme can spot irregularities in manufacturing in real-time and recognise patterns linked to previous food safety events. As an example, convolutional neural network (CNN) image analysis [14] may detect small imperfections or foreign items on food surfaces with high accuracy, which can aid in the prevention of substandard products from reaching consumers. Using deep learning technologies to improve product quality monitoring has become the cutting edge of food quality research. Recurrent neural networks (RNNs) [15] and long short-term memory networks (LSTMs) are examples of sequential models that can monitor several parameters in real-time on the production line; this allows for the acquisition of fine-grained classification of product appearance and quality aspects. An example of how convolutional neural networks trained on high-resolution pictures might enhance product quality is by detecting minute colour shifts or shape faults.

Digital Transformation in the Food Industry

The food business is experiencing a digital transformation due to the ever-increasing capabilities of technology [16]. Production efficiency has been greatly enhanced by automated and smart manufacturing technology, while consumer wants have been better understood with the help of big data analytics. Also, blockchain technology makes the supply chain more transparent and traceable, which is great for food safety. Conversely, cutting-edge tech is paving the way for futuristic food innovations like 3D-printed food and virtual reality.

This essay delves deeper into the topics of big data, blockchain, and artificial intelligence, highlighting their significant roles and advantages in the food industry. These technological shifts provide a firm foundation for using AI and big data.

Application of Forecasting Models and Machine Learning Algorithms in Demand Forecasting

The food business relies heavily on demand predictions [17] when making decisions. To avoid running out of stock or having too much inventory on hand, businesses can benefit from demand trend and change forecasts. Using relevant data like historical sales figures and industry trends, forecasting models and machine learning algorithms may build trustworthy demand forecasting models. Through data analysis and learning, these models and algorithms can automatically spot and document demand trends, make predictions, and provide personalised recommendations and decision-support.

Supply chain management using big data analytics, demand forecasting with predictive models and machine learning algorithms, and a deeper grasp of the customer demand scenario can all help food companies. This helps them meet consumer demand, boost operational efficiency, and delight customers. This will improve organisations' competitiveness by optimising production planning and supply chain management [18].

AI IN FOOD PRODUCTION: HOW IT HELPS WITH CYCLE OPTIMIZATION

Artificial intelligence technologies are becoming indispensable tools for the food manufacturing industry. These tools help optimise the production process, allowing producers to fulfil demand, eliminate waste, and assure product quality control. In the food manufacturing stage, artificial intelligence is in high demand and is only going to get bigger. From 2023–2032, the worldwide artificial intelligence industry is expected to grow from an initial valuation of over \$1.37B in 2022 to more than \$11.13B in 2032, a CAGR (Compound Annual Growth Rate) of 23.3%.

From planning to distribution, AI's revolutionary impact is felt thanks to a spectrum of solutions designed to address various difficulties experienced throughout the production cycle. Let's explore how AI changes things up at each step.

Planning and Forecasting

Problem: Companies in the food industry either make too much or too little food due to inaccurate demand predictions. This could lead to a loss of money and the squandering of resources.

Solution: The use of sophisticated statistical models, such as those used in time series analysis, and machine learning algorithms, such as neural networks and regression, are the building blocks of AI and ML systems. These algorithms analyse massive datasets that include past sales data, current market trends, and external variables like weather and holidays in order to reveal the big data impact on businesses.

In addition, AI uses predictive analytics, such as long short-term memory models and autoregressive integrated moving average, to adjust production plans in real-time to meet changes in consumer demand. To maximise profits and ensure optimal use of resources, experts in food production use cutting-edge optimisation algorithms such as gradient descent and genetic algorithms to optimise inventory levels while simultaneously reducing waste.

AI and ML for Restaurant Businesses: Optimization Solutions

Beyond just making food, AI has many other uses in the food business. It also presents a wealth of options for the restaurant industry, which can improve efficiency, delight customers, and increase profits. Now that we know what tools can assist with this, let's explore how AI and ML solutions are changing various parts of the restaurant industry.

Main Tasks AI Helps with For Restaurant Businesses

Fig 2: Main Tasks AI Helps with for Restaurant Businesses.

Inventory Management

The food sector relies on efficient inventory management to keep operations running smoothly and make the most of their profits. But, food companies frequently experience either an abundance of inventory or a lack of it. These obstacles are no longer an obstacle for restaurants because to cutting-edge AI technologies. We'll see how it works.

Problem: A typical problem for food firms is inaccurate inventory forecasting, which can cause waste, low service quality, or lost sales due to overstocking or stockouts. Because they depend on manual processes and historical data, traditional food sector inventory management solutions struggle to precisely forecast future demand and optimise inventory levels appropriately.

Solution: To harness the power of data and estimate demand with unparalleled accuracy, restaurants can leverage advanced AI/ML techniques like recurrent neural networks or time series forecasting models. In order to optimise inventory levels in the food business, these algorithms analyse customer data, seasonal trends, and even social media sentiment. The results are actionable insights. This guarantees that restaurants never run out of the proper goods and also cuts down on food waste.

Example: Among the many food sector solution providers, MarketMan and BlueCart stand out for their advanced inventory management systems driven by artificial intelligence. These systems optimise stock levels according to demand predictions, automate replenishment orders, and keep tabs on inventory levels in real time using predictive analytics that are comparable to those used in retail.

Menu Optimization

To remain competitive, increase profits, and revolutionise customer service, restaurants are embracing AI technologies to optimise their menus and pricing tactics. Now, let's examine the example in more detail.

Problem: Food companies frequently experience low profitability and customer unhappiness due to inefficient menu planning and pricing methods. The precision and agility needed to adjust to changing market conditions and guarantee customer satisfaction are lacking in several current methods of menu optimisation and pricing.

Solution: Now that AI can be used for analytics in the food business, menu planning and pricing tactics can be revolutionised. Sales figures, customer tastes, and ingredient prices are just a few examples of the massive volumes of data analysed by sophisticated ML algorithms. Food businesses may use AI to learn what customers like, what they order most often, and how to improve their menus by drawing useful conclusions from this data.

IMPLEMENTATION OF INDUSTRY 4.0 TECHNOLOGIES FOR FOOD SAFETY

The World Economic Forum described the Fourth Industrial Revolution (Figure 3) as "characterised by a fusion of technologies that is blurring the lines between the physical, digital, and biological spheres." This comes after mechanisation, industrialization, and automation, which were preceded by the steam engine, electricity, and production lines, respectively.

Figure 3. Industrial Revolutions Over Time

Industry 4.0 relies on a wide group of disruptive technologies such as:

- Internet of Things (IoT)
- Big Data
- Blockchain
- Advanced analytics
- Machine learning
- Artificial intelligence (AI)
- Simulation.

Nonetheless, technological advancements are only one facet of the Fourth Industrial Revolution. The chance to assist business moguls, government officials, and the general public in making the most of convergent technologies to build a future that is welcoming to everyone is here.

These emerging technologies have the potential to greatly improve food safety, especially in the food industry. The purpose of this piece is to offer:

- A brief description about how this is being (and can be) done
- How Industry 4.0 technologies are currently being applied across different links of the food supply chain
- A methodology for implementing a strong and effective Industry 4.0 strategy within a food business
- An outline of the potential benefits of Industry 4.0 to help drive food safety forward.

Industry 4.0 Maturity Levels

There has been very little widespread use of Industry 4.0 technology in the food business thus far. Research spanning the entire industry has shown that adoption rates in the food sector are between 20 and 40 percent, in the oil and gas sector they are over 80 percent, and in the automobile industry they are 45 to 60 percent. When we talk about technology adoption in the food industry, we're referring about the industry as a whole, not just in terms of food safety. A lot of work remains, but we have a fantastic chance to speed up the sector's adoption of Industry 4.0 technology. In addition, we may speed up our transition to Industry 4.0 technologies by studying the successes and failures of other industries, such the oil and gas, pharmaceutical, automotive, and information technology sectors.

Figure 4 shows that there are four stages of Industry 4.0 deployment that lead to improved food safety. Included in these stages of development are digitization (the process of automating data), digitalization (the integration of systems and data flows), automation (the reduction of human error through the automation of jobs), and culture (the shift from a reactive to a proactive, anticipatory, and finally predictive mentality in business).

Figure 4. Maturity Levels for Implementing Industry 4.0 for Better Food Safety

Currently, digitalization is being embraced by the food business. With predictive analytics being in its early stages and facing challenges with data integration, food firms are unable to fully utilise its potential. Automating incident prevention is mostly done on a regional level, and data leveraging as an income generator is rarely implemented.

Industry 4.0 Across the Food Supply Chain

Adopting Industry 4.0 technology throughout the food supply chain presents enormous opportunity to enhance food safety. Nevertheless, the possible advantages and their applicability differ substantially based on your position in the food supply chain.

The use of data-related Industry 4.0 technologies to improve food safety is becoming more common in many stages of the food supply chain, as shown in Table 1.

TABLE 1. Adoptions of Industry 4.0 Technologies for Food Safety

Supply Chain Link	Digitalize Data and Automate Data Collection			
Farming	Automated farm management systems to record practices	Precision agriculture: Use of remote sensing technologies and sensors to: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Detect crop and water contamination • Manage pest that might result in foodborne illness outbreak 		
R&D and Procurement	Electronic certificate of analysis to validate ingredients from suppliers	IoT (location, temperature) to prevent breaks in the cold chain and food fraud		
Processing and Manufacturing	Real-time inline measurement to detect issues more rapidly, control 100 percent of the production (e.g. temperature, humidity, gas presence, water quality, pesticide residues, air quality monitoring, material wear, usage time for machinery, etc.)	Error-proof workflow through digital and interactive SOPs , which ensure that operators have up-to-date information, prompt operators to take preventive or corrective actions, and make them accountable by asking them to log these actions	Augmented reality (for new operator training, or maintenance and audits by external parties) to limit exposure of persons and products to unnecessary risks	
Distribution, Logistics, and Retail	Digitalized management of stocks and expiration date of products	IoT sensors to help prevent breaks in the cold chain and food fraud	QR codes, (EAS) tags and RFID tags for traceability, and smart labels to detect food spoilage	Smartphone-based biosensors for onsite rapid pre-screening of food quality and safety parameters
Restaurants and Catering	Digitalized management of stocks and expiration dates of products	Smart kitchen equipment for monitoring time and temperature processes	Error-proof workflow through digital and interactive SOPs	AI and predictive analytics applied to managerial controls to monitor food safety practices in real time, correlate the data with food safety incidents, and prioritize internal audits and training
Regulators, Certification Bodies, and Auditors	Paperless trade (electronic SPS)	Augmented reality (for new operators, contractors, auditors, etc.) to limit exposure of persons and products to unnecessary risks		
Food Sector as a Whole	End-to-end traceability to allow faster root cause analysis and selective recall, as well as prevention of food fraud (through technologies such as RFID, blockchain, etc.)	Utilization of shopper cards in case of recalls		

How to Implement Industry 4.0 Technologies for Food Safety

The starting point for an organization's Industry 4.0 food safety journey is heavily dependent on its maturity, product mix, complexity, and technological know-how. Problems with data and technology, out-of-date systems, fragmentation, or data quality and integrity could befall frontrunners. The absence of a digital strategy, a culture that values quality and safety, and antiquated systems are likely to be the primary challenges faced by less established food enterprises. Additionally, our research has shown that smaller businesses, especially new entrepreneurial startups, are more adaptable, receptive, and flexible when it comes to implementing Industry 4.0 food safety systems and technologies. This is partly due to the fact that the investments needed are smaller, even though the overall cost barrier is still steep. There is a correlation between the size of a food company's operations and the amount of investment needed, with larger companies having access to more capital and technological expertise, but internal bureaucracy can slow things down.

Industry 4.0 may be effectively implemented by businesses of any size or stage of development; in fact, there are a number of best practices that can be applied by any food industry to maximise the return on investment of their investments.

To successfully integrate Industry 4.0 Food Safety technology, we advise firms to think about the following phases (Figure 5).

Figure 5. Steps to Implement Industry 4.0 Food Safety Technologies.

Potential Benefits of Industry 4.0

Industry 4.0 technology adoption for food safety is in its early stages, but organisations are beginning to reap substantial benefits from a well-thought-out plan. There are a number of these, including:

- Making it easier to track and improve transparency.
- Ensuring the quality and safety of food items through the use of repeatable processes that provide consistent results.
- Making parametric product releases possible.
- Increasingly the robustness of products and processes by bolstering predictive capacities.
- Backing efforts to make food safer and of higher quality.

Accomplishing these advantages calls for the correct frame of mind and actions, in addition to real-time product and process monitoring, linked data, risk-based modelling integrated throughout the value chain, and automation.

Using AI and ML-Powered FoodTech Solutions in Everyday Life

In addition to helping big food corporations improve their operations, AI and ML also completely revamp industrial-scale food production. In addition, they could greatly improve our day-to-day adventures. There is a vast diversity of applications for ML/AI technologies that support individual preferences and needs, from optimising domestic chores and daily schedules to providing personalised dietary advice and it was shown in figure 6.

How AI-Powered FoodTech Solutions Are Used Daily

Fig 6: AI powered FoodTech solutions

Personalized Nutrition Recommendations

AI and ML technologies are revolutionizing nutrition by providing personalized recommendations tailored to individual needs and preferences.

- AI algorithms analyze user data to tailor personalized recommendations based on dietary habits, health conditions, and goals.
- Predictive analytics forecast how foods impact health outcomes, promoting informed dietary choices and helping to move from junk food to healthy food products.
- AI technology creates personalized meal plans tailored to users' goals, whether it's weight loss, muscle gain, or simply switching to healthy foods.
- Continuous learning enables AI systems to refine recommendations over time, ensuring relevance and effectiveness.

Smart Kitchen Appliances

With AI and ML capabilities, kitchen appliances are becoming smarter, providing personalized cooking experiences, and optimizing resource utilization.

- AI in the food industry allows upgrading kitchen appliances into intelligent devices by integrating sensors, cameras, and connectivity features to understand and respond to users' needs.
- Smart kitchen appliances suggest recipes based on consumer preferences, ingredient availability, and dietary goals, utilizing data from recipe databases and user feedback.
- Artificial intelligence with predictive analytics anticipates cooking times and temperature adjustments by analysing historical recipe data and user interactions.
- Smart appliances refine recipe recommendations and cooking techniques over time by learning from user interactions and feedback.

Food Waste Reduction

AI and ML are helping reduce food waste by optimizing meal planning and grocery shopping processes.

- AI meal planning apps optimize meal plans by analysing ingredient availability, expiration dates, and user preferences to reduce waste.
- Artificial intelligence grocery platforms recommend optimal quantities based on past purchases and household size, minimizing overstocking and food spoilage.
- AI also helps to reduce food waste, when it adapts to user preferences over time by analysing interactions and feedback, refining suggestions, and providing personalized tips.

Recipe Recommendation and Cooking Assistance

Platforms powered by artificial intelligence are revolutionizing cooking by offering personalized recipe suggestions and real-time assistance to users of all skill levels.

- ML algorithms analyse user data to understand food products preferences and skill levels, tailoring recipe recommendations accordingly.
- AI recipe recommendation platforms generate personalized suggestions aligned with users' preferences and dietary goals.
- AI cooking assistance tools offer step-by-step guidance and real-time feedback to help users achieve optimal results.
- AI in the food industry continuously improves recommendations based on user interactions and feedback to better meet users' needs over time.

CONCLUSION

In the food business, the fusion of AI and machine learning is a game-changer, providing creative answers to urgent problems and promoting long-term expansion. Across the industry, AI and ML are revolutionising food safety, food manufacturing methods, waste minimization, and sales optimisation.

Accurate demand forecasting, inventory control, and supply chain management are made easier in the food business by AI. Additionally, it gives food producers more authority to improve sustainable farming methods and manage concerns associated with climate change. Furthermore, to support healthier lifestyles, AI and ML promise individualised nutrition recommendations, smart kitchen appliances, and cooking assistance platforms for customers and businesses.

Nonetheless, issues like poor data quality, intricate food systems, difficulty adhering to regulations, and a lack of skilled workers continue to exist. To get past these obstacles and create an atmosphere that supports ML and AI innovation in the food sector, cooperation is required. The food sector may move towards a sustainable future that is technologically sophisticated, ecologically conscientious, and socially responsible by making effective use of AI and ML technology. We would be happy to assist your food and restaurant business on its journey towards intelligent transformation with our AI/ML software developers!

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